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AdvanCing behavioural
Change Through
an INclusive Green deal

Deliverable 5.5: Research Agendas - 2nd cycle

SEERC

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List of Acronyms

BUIs	Bottom-Up Initiatives
CGs	Community Gardens
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
ESCOs	Energy Service Companies
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
PA	Pilot Action
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises

The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

ACCTING explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. The project collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

Project Consortium

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Summary

- Existing interventions often fail to capture how overlapping disadvantages, such as gender, socio-economic status, and migration, exacerbate climate-related risks. Future research could focus on mapping these compounded vulnerabilities in different contexts and developing data-driven strategies to address them in policy design.
- Individual awareness campaigns cannot achieve persistent change in sustainability practices if broader institutional and infrastructural support are lacking. Future research could explore how longitudinal, multi-level interventions (including peer-learning platforms, community-led projects, and policy incentives) foster enduring pro-environmental behaviours.
- Unclear policies and limited outreach restrict the participation of low-income, migrant, and otherwise marginalized groups in clean-energy initiatives. Future research could identify effective trust-building mechanisms, culturally sensitive outreach methods, and cross-governance collaboration that facilitate equitable involvement in community energy projects.
- Resource-constrained small enterprises, especially those led by women and migrants, struggle to adopt sustainable practices due to limited financial support, networks, and institutional backing. Future research could investigate how tailored credit models, mentorship programs, and cooperative networks help micro-entrepreneurs expand their resilience and foster local green innovations.
- Bottom-up initiatives often do not reach socially vulnerable populations, and conventional approaches to climate activism overlook the roles of certain groups, such as fathers or extended family networks. Future research could explore scalable frameworks, like community-based food production or equitable bike-sharing schemes, that involve diverse actors and address both affordability and inclusivity.
- There is limited insight into how policymaker motivations, political constraints, and socio-cultural factors converge to determine whether equitable, car-free measures are implemented or resisted. Future research could delve into comparative analyses of policymaker decision-making processes, examining how institutional capacities, stakeholder alliances, and cultural norms either enable or impede the uptake of inclusive and low-car mobility solutions.

1. Introduction

1.1 Overview

This report is the final output of Task 5.3 Developing Future Research Agendas (M18–M40), the second of two major deliverables that synthesize the findings from the ACCTING project's iterative research and experimental activities. Building on the first report's insights, this second report captures the enhanced knowledge generated through the second cycle research activities in WP3 and the Open Studios in WP4, as well as insights from WP5 over the Pilot Actions that directly engaged stakeholders in testing intervention strategies.

The present report extends the outcomes of earlier work by deriving new conclusions from additional case studies, co-design processes, and real-world pilot implementations. These additional data, derived from community experiences and collaborative experiments, enhance our comprehension of how future actions might fairly support the implementation of Green Deal policies.

Within the framework of Task 5.3, this second report pursues two primary objectives, building on the project's iterative and cumulative research process. First, it aims to reassess and refine existing knowledge gaps by drawing on new insights generated through the second cycle of research and Open Studios. In doing so, it evaluates how previously identified challenges have evolved or persisted over time, while also highlighting additional questions that emerged during the implementation of the Pilot Actions. Second, the report sets out future research directions, leveraging the empirical evidence gathered from testing various solutions in real-world settings. These targeted research avenues are designed to meet immediate policy demands while addressing longer-term social and environmental imperatives, with a particular emphasis on strategies that promote inclusivity in climate action and attend to context-specific barriers.

1.2 Approach and Methodology

The process of developing these future research agendas is grounded in the ACCTING project's overarching methodology, which combines collaborative research, participatory action, and iterative pilot testing. Building on the foundations set in the first cycle, the second cycle of activities (encompassing additional fieldwork, case studies, and Open Studios) has further refined and expanded the evidence base regarding Green Deal interventions and the socio-economic inequalities they can address or exacerbate.

Essentially, this second cycle incorporated higher levels of stakeholder engagement (ranging from policy practitioners and civil society organizations to local communities) through Pilot Actions implemented across diverse socio-geographic settings. These pilot actions were designed to test specific interventions, gather real-world feedback, and surface both expected and unexpected outcomes. The findings inform new lines of inquiry

around policy impacts, participatory governance, and inclusive behavioural change strategies.

The final step consisted of synthesizing the insights gleaned from the second cycle of research and Open Studios (alongside the cumulative findings from earlier phases) into a cohesive, updated framework for future research agendas. As part of this synthesis, the newly identified knowledge gaps were reconciled with those arising from the Pilot Actions, ultimately yielding six core research themes. An initial draft of the research agendas was then constructed, reflecting these themes and incorporating feedback from researchers across the relevant thematic lines. Following this internal consolidation, the draft agendas were presented at the partner workshop in January 2025, where interdisciplinary working groups critiqued and refined them by identifying cross-cutting issues, thematic overlaps, contradictions, and opportunities for intersectional analysis. The workshop facilitated an exchange of perspectives, ensuring that the revised framework remained both evidence-based and responsive to the complexities of diverse research lines. Following these discussions, the project team identified an additional research theme, bringing the total number of themes to seven:

1. Local Communities and Disasters
2. Sustainability, transformation, and behavioural change
3. Transformative Behavioural Change for Energy and Solidarity Communities
4. Bridging Environmental Sustainability and Social Inclusion in Vulnerable Micro-Entrepreneurship
5. Inclusive and Sustainable Food Systems
6. Inclusive and Sustainable Mobility
7. Complexity of Intersectional Vulnerabilities

The final draft underwent another iterative round of feedback among the various research groups, culminating in a cohesive and unified set of research agendas.

In practice, this iterative, multi-method approach ensures that the future research agendas proposed herein not only build on ACCTING's original evidence base but also reflect the new realities and lessons discovered through hands-on implementation. The aim is to offer a dynamically evolving body of knowledge that can inform policymakers, practitioners, and researchers as they work to align sustainability goals with social justice imperatives in the ongoing development of the European Green Deal.

2. Future Research Directions

2.1 Theme 1: Local Communities and Disasters

This theme explores how local communities experience, prepare for, and respond to climate-related disasters. It focuses on the forms of knowledge, social capital, and agency that emerge at the local level, and the barriers these communities face in participating in formal disaster risk reduction frameworks. The theme also considers the potential for inclusive strategies that integrate local perspectives into Green Deal implementation and climate adaptation policies.

2.1.1 Relevant Findings

- Local communities hold valuable insights for mitigating and adapting and responding to climate-change-related disasters. However, their knowledge is often undervalued or insufficiently integrated into formal disaster management systems.
- Institutional change is needed to make the most of local social networks, material practices and knowledge systems.
- Gender and intersectional vulnerabilities remain insufficiently explored in disaster management. Gender+ considerations are crucial, as disasters disproportionately impact women, the elderly, disabled individuals, and marginalized groups.
- Women play critical but undervalued roles in community-level disaster prevention, preparedness and response, e.g., performing unseen and unrecognised work to strengthen and maintain social and material infrastructures.
- Women in leadership roles were crucial to some of the most successful examples of community organising.
- While authorities may recognize the value of local knowledge and inclusiveness, many fail to integrate it into their disaster management policies due to structural and institutional hinders, such as a lack of economic resources, bureaucratic rigidity and a top-down, paternalistic approach.
- Local knowledge is sometimes dismissed as unscientific or impractical, highlighting a disconnect between universal best practice and the context of policy implementation.
- Community organising has successfully filled gaps in disaster preparedness and response, especially in rural and under-resourced areas, e.g., community-led fire responses in Turkey and Sweden, and citizen-led flood monitoring committees in Italy.
- Vulnerabilities are exacerbated by systemic inequalities, such as socio-economic disadvantages, gender norms, and the exclusion of marginalized groups (like migrants) from decision-making.

- Migrant and minority communities often face heightened disaster risks due to housing in unsafe areas and limited access to information and resources.
- Many of the most successful and inclusive engagements between authorities and local communities involved hybrid authorities (e.g. multi-stakeholder expert groups), and mid-level mediators (e.g., community sentinels and spokespersons).
- Resilience was most evident when robust social and material infrastructures enabled a variety of interacting state and voluntary organisations to anticipate and respond to disaster in different ways (e.g., the Ljusdal case study).

2.1.2 Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Empowering Local Knowledge

Local communities possess valuable, context-specific knowledge regarding disaster prevention, preparedness and response. However, this knowledge is often overlooked or inadequately integrated into formal disaster management systems (Paudel et al., 2024). Bridging this gap is essential to strengthen community resilience.

Research questions:

- How can local knowledge be effectively incorporated into disaster risk reduction (DRR) policies and frameworks?
- What epistemic practices and institutional mechanisms are needed to bridge the gap between expert-driven approaches and community insights?

Subtheme 2. Gender+ Intersectionality

Disasters disproportionately affect women, the elderly, and other marginalized groups (Neumayer & Plümpert 2007). Understanding how gender and intersectional vulnerabilities affect the possibility for mitigation and adaptation is key to more inclusive disaster management strategies.

Research questions:

- How do intersecting social vulnerabilities influence disaster risk and response capabilities?
- What policies and practices can ensure the meaningful inclusion of marginalized groups in disaster preparedness?

Subtheme 3. Institutional Adaptation

Despite the recognition of local knowledge, inflexible bureaucratic systems may resist bottom-up, community-led approaches to disaster risk reduction (DRR). Institutional adaptation is necessary for fostering more inclusive and participatory disaster management strategies (Molina et. al., 2016).

Research questions:

- What cultural and structural changes are required to facilitate institutional adaptation in DRR?

- How can participatory models be scaled to enhance inclusiveness in disaster management?

Subtheme 4. Community-Driven Initiatives

Grassroots and community-driven initiatives play a crucial role in disaster management, particularly in under-resourced areas (e.g., flood monitoring committees in Calabria, forest protection groups in rural Romania, etc.). However, these initiatives often lack long-term support and recognition from formal authorities, hindering their sustainability (Wolff et al., 2021).

Research questions:

- What funding and support programmes can sustain community-driven disaster preparedness efforts?
- How can authorities create the regulatory conditions that encourage and not foreclose community organising for DRR?

Subtheme 5. Addressing Systemic Inequalities

Disaster vulnerability is often compounded by socio-economic inequalities, with marginalized groups facing greater risks due to limited access to resources and decision-making power. Addressing these systemic inequalities is essential for effective disaster resilience.

Research questions:

- What role can DRR policies and practices play in addressing intersecting social inequalities?
- How can policies for the broad social transformation that is needed to address social vulnerabilities and prevent disaster be properly integrated into existing state and regulatory responsibilities?

Subtheme 6. Behavioural and Social Change

Behavioural change in the context of disaster preparedness and response can occur both individually and collectively (Pelling 2010). A deeper exploration of the dynamics between individual action, and community and social transformation is needed to identify effective strategies.

Research questions:

- How can individual and collective behavioural change complement each other in enhancing disaster prevention, preparedness and response?
- What are the most effective ways to engage individuals and communities in long-term disaster mitigation and adaptation strategies?

Subtheme 7. Youth Engagement and Intergenerational Knowledge

Young people, as well as the generational divide, have a crucial role in shaping future disaster resilience. Understanding their perspectives, as well as how to engage them in disaster preparedness, is vital.

Research questions:

- How can youth be more effectively involved in community-based disaster management strategies?
- What role does intergenerational learning play in building resilience in vulnerable communities?

Subtheme 8. Polarization in Disaster Management

Political polarization and state dysfunction hinder community collaboration and effective risk reduction. Research into strategies for overcoming political partisanship and conflict in the context of climate-change-related disaster in Europe is needed.

Research questions:

- What are the most effective strategies for overcoming polarization in disaster management and collaborating across different groups?
- How do political conflict and consensus shape community participation in DRR?

2.2 Theme 2: Local environmental stewardship - Sustainability, transformation and behavioural change

This theme explores how pro-nature behaviour change emerges from community-level engagement, cultural practices, and intergenerational transmission. It highlights the importance of understanding environmental action not as isolated individual choice, but as embedded in social structures and collective knowledge.

2.2.1 Relevant Findings

- The emergence of pro-nature behavioural change, particularly in vulnerable communities, is closely tied to cultural capital, role models, all inspiring and enabling the appearance of strong group activities. Traditional practices and intergenerational knowledge are important ingredients for pro-environment behavioural change and an inclusive discourse. Triggers for engagement and change are strongly linked to the neighbourhood e.g. the village.
- ⊘ Effective knowledge sharing in movements focusing on environmental stewardship ignites participation and enables deeper individual or group transformation. However, gaps exist in the accessibility and practical application of special knowledge within communities. Identifying and re-visiting earlier experiences and knowledge but activating peer- networks contribute to enhance maturity of initiatives.
- Vulnerable groups face challenges in participation due to systemic barriers like socio-economic inequalities, lack of institutional support, and knowledge gaps. Our 11 cases show multiple vulnerabilities occurring from ethnic groups and status, lived tradition, gendered perspectives and especially rurality. Empowering these groups requires inclusive approaches, empathy and sensitive engagement patterns including e.g. a place based, neighbourhood solidarity discourse.
- Inclusive approaches with respecting differences, the special role of women, local non-privileged groups create durable activist movements. Female leadership re-percuss the neighbourhood presence and integrate an active gendered voice, often different from the market or job-income logic. Hence, unique barriers for participants occur across multiple and overlapping vulnerabilities and empowerment by external moderators can bridge existing gaps.
- Results of societal transformation beyond local neighbourhood concerns occur with previous empowering experience. The appearance of a true discourse about a possible inclusive future leaving no one behind creates shared resilience patterns. Project based action and urgent activist action create a productive discourse, capacities to initiate a durable change and to capitalize upon this discourse request special efforts - often beyond the intentions of focused movements. Anchoring new activities, capitalizing on this resource is an inseparable ingredient of durable pro-environment behaviour.

2.2.2 Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Traditions and intergenerational exchange for sustainability

Understanding how traditional practice and contemporary environmental action can positively interrelate is vital for the advancement of sustainable behaviours, particularly in vulnerable communities (Gómez-Baggethun et al., 2013). Research on intergenerational knowledge dynamics can further inform pro-environment patterns for behavioural change.

Research questions:

- How does traditional practice integrate with contemporary pro-environmental action and changing demands?
- What role do cultural and intergenerational narratives play in fostering pro-nature behaviours in vulnerable communities?

Subtheme 2. Knowledge Sharing and Transformation

Knowledge sharing is an important component of building up durable pro-environmental stewardship and collective action. However, there are gaps in accessibility and the practical application of environmental knowledge, particularly within communities facing socio-economic challenges (Fazey et al., 2013).

Research questions:

- How can peer exchange or digital marketplaces enhance environmental knowledge-sharing among communities?
- What are the determining barriers for functioning knowledge transfer processes in pro-nature initiatives?

Subtheme 3. Gender and intersectionality in environmental initiatives

Gender-specific factors and intersectional vulnerabilities influence the appearance and build-up; the ability to participate in environmental initiatives (Kaijser & Kronsell 2014); and finally, the wider impact of initiatives. Understanding the gender dynamics of the build-up phase and durable action can lead to more equitable and inclusive pro-environment activities.

Research questions:

- How do intersectional vulnerabilities influence engagement in pro-nature initiatives in leading positions and what specific challenges do women face in leadership roles in environmental movements?
- How can successful leadership patterns and role models appear that link to durable action?

Subtheme 4. Participation Challenges and Inclusivity

Systemic barriers hinder marginalised groups, rural people or traditional culture practicing groups from participation in environmental initiatives. To increase inclusivity, robust evidence frameworks are needed that capture diverse voices e.g. in support programmes.

Over time this can guide steps to empower vulnerable groups to take part in sustainability efforts.

Research questions:

- How can inclusive frameworks of pro-nature engagement be developed that address participation barriers?
- What role can institutional and project-based support play in empowering marginalised groups and what are fitting indicators for inclusive participation?

Subtheme 5. Tension between economic and environmental impacts on neighbourhoods

Tensions between economic prosperity and environmental sustainability are a significant challenge, especially in vulnerable communities and when affecting living places, neighbourhoods (Martinez-Alier et al., 2010). Exploring how those tensions are perceived in the community but also how such situations are contextualised, operationalised by powerful business players can inspire new insights. Understanding powerful players and their influence on neighbourhoods under pressure is an important determinant to understand barriers for a more inclusive participation in pro-environment action.

Research questions:

- How do dedicated resistive communities address the tension between environmental sustainability and the interests of economic players, especially in economically disadvantaged areas?
- What is the evidence for successful strategies of administrations to balance successfully economic pressures with sustainability goals in areas with presence of vulnerable groups?

Subtheme 6. Re-building Environmental Stewardship

Traditional use practice and new practice of civil society engagement for the environment have important roles for building up environmental stewardship, particularly for marginalised and vulnerable groups (Berkes et al., 2007). Research can contribute to assess the impact of current pro-environment action and identify effective ways to move from short term urgent civic action to durable long-term models of engagement leading to sustained behavioural change.

Research questions:

- What are proven pathways to best embed durable environmental engagement in vulnerable communities and what are critical success factors, benchmarks for durable initiatives?
- How do conceptually recently applied approaches as the natural commons, the multispecies dimension or participatory governance integrate effectively with pro-nature action involving vulnerable groups?

2.3 Theme 3: Transformative Behavioural Change for Energy and Solidarity Communities

This research theme explores how energy communities that wish to pursue societal goals (so called: Energy and Solidarity Communities or inclusive energy communities) can serve as catalysts for sustainable practices and social inclusion, focusing on the transformative behavioural changes needed to achieve equitable and environmentally conscious outcomes. It examines the dynamics of individual and collective behaviour, the barriers and enablers to participation among people who experiment with disadvantageous conditions, and the structural and policy frameworks required to support inclusive and scalable energy solutions. By addressing these dimensions, the theme seeks to identify actionable pathways for supporting resilient and socially equitable energy transitions.

2.3.1 Relevant Findings

- People in disadvantageous conditions had often limited prior knowledge of sustainability practices, which impacted their engagement. However, targeted workshops and meetings improved participation rates and fostered a sense of community.
- Direct support, both in terms of funding and consultancy, and active communication may enhance vulnerable individuals' inclusion. Trust in project leaders was a crucial factor for involvement, particularly in projects targeting energy poverty.
- Intersectionality emerges as a key factor, with women and individuals from minority backgrounds facing distinct challenges and opportunities within energy communities.
- Behavioural adaptation was often driven by economic necessity rather than environmental awareness, where residents reduced energy usage to cut costs.
- Social interactions and communal activities may be effective in teaching sustainability practices and fostering pro-environmental behaviour.
- Educational efforts and participatory governance can sustain long-term behavioural change among members.
- Municipal and organizational support plays a critical role in project success, but unclear national policies on energy communities hinder broader scalability.
- Financial challenges, such as the lack of subsidized programs for vulnerable groups, were a recurring issue across case studies.
- Local leadership and dedicated governance are important in overcoming structural barriers and engaging people in disadvantageous conditions.

2.3.2 Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1: Social Inclusion in Energy Communities

Energy and solidarity communities are increasingly recognized for their potential to alleviate energy poverty and foster sustainable development (Koukoulou et al., 2023), yet their capacity to include marginalized groups remains uneven. Low-income families, and immigrants often face systemic barriers (such as language constraints, cultural isolation, and limited social capital) that hinder full participation in community energy initiatives (Boostani et al., 2024). Moreover, a lack of trust in local governance or project coordinators may exacerbate these exclusions, particularly where historically underserved populations perceive initiatives as elitist or inaccessible (Grossmann et al., 2021). Even when technical solutions and financial support mechanisms are available, meaningful engagement can be undermined by inadequate outreach and the absence of culturally sensitive communication strategies (Lakhan, 2024). These challenges point to the urgent need for more comprehensive, bottom-up approaches that address intersectional vulnerabilities and ensure that energy and solidarity communities truly embody principles of equity and empowerment.

Research Questions:

Contextual and Cultural Barriers

- How do social and cultural contexts influence the participation of people in disadvantageous conditions in energy communities?
- What mechanisms ensure equitable involvement of people in disadvantageous conditions, such as single-parent households and immigrants, in energy community projects?

Trust-Building Strategies

- How does trust impact long-term participation and commitment in energy communities?
- What are the critical trust-building factors between energy community leaders, policymakers, and vulnerable groups?

Intersectionality and Gender

- How can gender+ intersectional approaches can reshape participation dynamics in energy communities?
- What specific outreach and engagement strategies can address the unique barriers faced by women, migrants, and other intersectionally vulnerable groups?

Incentives facilitating the engagement of people in disadvantageous conditions

- What kind of incentives (financial subsidies, capacity-building programs, easing of regulatory requirements) can most effectively facilitate the participation of people in disadvantageous conditions in energy communities?

- How can public and private funding, including corporate social responsibility (CSR) and impact investment, be harnessed to subsidize membership and initial costs for those most in need?

Leveraging Existing Community Schemes

- Can energy and solidarity communities be built using other already successful local community structures (e.g., housing cooperatives, local cultural or sports clubs)?
- How can these existing networks accelerate trust, reduce administrative hurdles, and promote knowledge-sharing for sustainable energy practices?

Subtheme 2: Behavioural Adaptation and Sustainability Practices

Despite various initiatives aimed at encouraging pro-environmental habits, long-term adoption of such practices among energy community members remains limited and sometimes inconsistent. Although financial incentives and technological support can generate initial uptake, the deeper dynamics of knowledge transfer, social cohesion, and lived experiences are under-examined (Lennon et al., 2020; Smith & Tidwell, 2016). Community-led workshops and peer-learning forums can foster a collective identity, yet their sustained impact depends on how well new behaviours align with everyday routines, cultural norms, and individuals' sense of agency (Baasch and Maschke, 2025). To address these gaps, longitudinal research that captures not just the early success of sustainability programs but also the evolving relationships, power dynamics, and personal narratives is necessary for understanding how pro-environmental actions can become deeply rooted.

Research Questions:

Scalability and Inclusivity

- How can successful community-based energy models be scaled while maintaining inclusivity and equitable benefits?
- What role does peer learning and cross-community exchange play in promoting scalable solutions?

Sustaining Engagement Over Time

- How do energy communities sustain inclusivity and engagement across diverse member profiles over time?
- Can the example of energy and solidarity communities act as a catalyst for wider environmental agency of vulnerable groups (e.g., spillover of pro-environmental behaviours into other social or environmental fields)?

Communication and Outreach

- What are the most effective messaging strategies to resonate with economically constrained individuals and underscore both financial and environmental benefits?

- How do local leaders and champions shape narratives around green transitions that motivate long-term behavioural change rather than short-term cost savings alone?

Subtheme 3: Policy and Structural Drivers of Behavioural Change

Recent scholarship on energy communities has emphasized their potential to democratize clean energy and alleviate energy poverty. Nonetheless, policy frameworks commonly lack explicit requirements or incentives to ensure that disadvantaged and low-income groups can participate (Lennon et al., 2019). In many regions, government guidelines fail to define eligibility criteria, participation quotas, or decision-making processes that prioritize marginalized populations, leaving also the communities that at least formally pursue societal goals at risk of exclusion of disadvantaged people (Wahlund and Palm, 2022; Campos and Marín-González, 2023). Insufficient information on cost-sharing arrangements, along with complex administrative processes, reduces the ease of participation for individuals lacking initial resources or technical proficiency (Sovacool et al., 2021). Thus, instead of mitigating inequalities, current regulatory frameworks may reinforce them by privileging individuals with the resources and knowledge to navigate bureaucratic obstacles and obtain financial support, thereby undermining the equity aims that energy communities are allegedly meant to serve.

Research Questions:

Effective Policy Frameworks

- What policy frameworks are most effective in promoting the inclusion of people in disadvantageous conditions in energy and solidarity communities?
- How can local governance structures and financial incentives be optimized to support energy and solidarity community scalability?

Municipal and Administrative Support

- What role do municipal policies play in reducing the bureaucratic and financial barriers to the establishment of energy communities?
- How can local policymakers embark on a deliberative process that genuinely engages people in disadvantageous conditions, and what are the boundaries of resilience in this context?

Private Sector Engagement and CSR

- How can private-sector key players (e.g., banks, energy production/distribution companies) facilitate the inclusion of people in disadvantageous conditions, in energy communities and so, facilitate their evolution towards energy and solidarity communities?
- Can this engagement be integrated within their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Impactful Investment schemes to ensure long-term support?

Public-Private Partnerships

- Can the financial burden of inclusive energy communities be met through the involvement of private actors such as energy companies and commercial renewable energy developers?
- What are the best governance models (public, private, or hybrid) to ensure transparency, accountability, and equitable cost-sharing?

Technology Accessibility and Circular Approaches

- How can technologies (e.g., photovoltaic panels, smart meters) be made more affordable and accessible to energy communities while responding to their specific needs?
- What role could recycling, reusing, or the “maker/DIY” movement play in lowering barriers to entry and fostering local innovation in green energy transitions?

2.4 Theme 4: Bridging Environmental Sustainability and Social Inclusion in Vulnerable Micro-Entrepreneurship

This theme addresses the integration of social and environmental objectives for micro-entrepreneurs who operate under resource constraints. It explores the systemic, behavioural, and policy factors that can enable or hinder the transition to sustainable practices, focusing particularly on vulnerable groups such as migrants, low-income entrepreneurs, and women-led enterprises.

2.4.1 Relevant Findings

- Across the 21 ACCTING case studies, entrepreneurs frequently cited difficulties in securing financial support for sustainability measures, such as energy-efficient equipment and renewable energy solutions.
- Informal enterprises, particularly in Belgium and Norway, lacked access to formal financial systems, further exacerbating their vulnerabilities.
- Entrepreneurs in Greece and Romania showed interest in adopting sustainable practices but lacked technical knowledge and understanding of available incentives. Peer learning and brainstorming sessions, as facilitated by the ACCTING project, proved effective in introducing practical solutions to micro-entrepreneurs.
- Resilience to financial and policy shocks varied among the cases, with enterprises in Romania demonstrating higher adaptability through integrated sustainability approaches.
- Entrepreneurs in Belgium and Norway highlighted difficulties in expanding their operations while maintaining sustainability due to high costs and fragmented support systems.

2.4.2 Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1: Overcoming Structural Barriers

Micro-entrepreneurs in unstable circumstances frequently struggle with structural limitations that hinder their capacity to implement sustainable practices. These systemic barriers include insufficient capital reserves and financial flows, lack of qualified human resources, heightened risk perceptions, and fragmented support networks, which collectively limit both the exploration and implementation of green innovations (Moore and Manring, 2009). Even when opportunities for environmental retrofitting or adoption of renewable energy technologies arise, the lack of assets, high interest rates, and lack of information and support from competent people restrict their access to formal credit and knowledge resources. In many cases, these entrepreneurs must prioritize immediate financial viability over medium/longer-term environmental investments, creating a loop in which resource limitations hinder the development or expansion of sustainable business models (Chien et al., 2021). As a result, the potential for micro-enterprises to drive local sustainability transitions remains underrealized, underscoring the need for integrated

policy support to help vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs bridge systemic gaps and progress toward environmentally resilient operations.

Research Questions:

Intersection of Environmental Investments and Socio-Economic Constraints

- How do environmental investments intersect with socio-economic constraints, and what adaptive strategies can enable micro-enterprises to optimize both sustainability and resilience?

Transformative Policy Frameworks

- What transformative policy frameworks and mechanisms can be designed to address the intersectional needs of micro-enterprises operating within resource-constrained environments?

Alignment with Lived Realities

- To what extent do existing support systems (e.g., incentives, subsidies, and training) align with the lived realities of vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs, and how can these systems be reimaged to foster equitable green transitions?

Institutions and Intermediaries

- Which institutions (e.g., local chambers of commerce, ESCOs, larger enterprises in their same value-chain, NGOs, cooperative banks, and municipal agencies) can act as facilitators or intermediary organizations for the green energy transition of micro-enterprises?
- How networks among SMEs can facilitate the green energy transition of micro-enterprises?
- How can local policymakers create administrative arrangements that ease access to credit, training, and mentorship for vulnerable entrepreneurs?

Subtheme 2: Behavioural Spillovers and Network Dynamics in Micro-Entrepreneurial Ecosystems

The adoption of sustainable practices by micro-enterprises can yield critical spillover effects among broader stakeholder networks, yet limited knowledge exists regarding how these changes diffuse across interconnected economic and social structures. Because micro-enterprises are sometimes (far from ever) deeply integrated with local ecosystems of employees, suppliers, and customers, shifts toward resource-efficient production and low-carbon solutions have the potential to generate further modifications in operating routines, procurement patterns, and consumption norms (Rosário et al., 2022). However, emerging evidence suggests that distinct network characteristics (particularly trust-based ties, supportive policy environments, and shared learning platforms) can significantly determine whether initial steps toward sustainability foster deeper transformative change or remain isolated to a few early adopters (Journeault et al., 2021). Adopting a multi-level perspective that accounts for the interplay of cultural, organizational, and market factors is thus crucial for tracing the ripple effects of green behaviours and designing interventions that amplify positive outcomes. Without such integrated analysis, policy measures risk

overlooking the subtle ways in which micro-enterprise ecosystems shape, and are simultaneously shaped by, evolving sustainability practices.

Research Questions:

Spillover Effects

- How do sustainability behaviours adopted by micro-entrepreneurs trigger adaptive responses among employees, suppliers, and customers?

Experimental Interventions

- What experimental interventions (e.g., nudges, peer-learning initiatives) can amplify positive behavioural spillovers across ecosystems?

Trust and Reciprocity

- How do micro-entrepreneurs' perceptions of trust and reciprocity shape their willingness to engage in sustainability-oriented networks?
- What digital and non-digital platforms can be designed to facilitate inclusive and trust-based collaborations for sustainability?

Messaging and Conflict Resolution

- How to overcome conflicting views on “traditional energy usage” and build trust in the green transition among micro-enterprises with limited human and financial resources?
- What are the most effective messages or signals to society that can legitimize and support vulnerable entrepreneurs' green transition efforts?

Subtheme 3: Enhancing Resilience and Scalability

Vulnerable micro-enterprises, often operating with limited financial reserves and restricted access to supportive networks, frequently encounter substantial obstacles in maintaining environmentally responsible practices over time (Chien et al., 2021). External shocks, such as economic recessions, pandemics, or fluctuating policy incentives, can worsen the vulnerability of these ventures, forcing owners to redirect scarce capital away from sustainability measures. Even when these enterprises manage to adopt more sustainable processes, such as installing energy-efficient technologies or integrating circular economy principles, the lack of supportive institutional frameworks and fragmented policy incentives makes it difficult to scale these practices effectively (Amato and Candio, 2024). Moreover, stakeholders in local ecosystems (suppliers, financial institutions, and municipal agencies) may be uncoordinated, further hindering access to sustained technical or financial assistance.

Without robust capacity-building programs, micro-grants, and targeted mentorship schemes, these ventures are vulnerable to reverting to previous traditional practices once the initial drive for sustainability diminishes. Furthermore, uncertainty around consumer demand for green products or services can dissuade entrepreneurs from committing resources to environmental improvements that may not yield immediate returns (Lee and Klassen, 2008). This cyclical pattern underscores the need for comprehensive policy interventions, including public-private partnerships and participatory governance models,

that buffer against market fluctuations and enable micro-enterprises to retain a commitment to green transitions. Conversely, through integrated support structures (i.e. a supportive institutional framework concluding local chambers of commerce, ESCOs, larger enterprises in their same value-chain, NGOs, cooperative banks, and municipal agencies) micro-entrepreneurs can more effectively mitigate risks, foster innovation, and ultimately build resilience against economic and ecological uncertainties.

Research Questions:

Resilience under Constraints

- What factors contribute to the resilience of micro-enterprises in sustaining and advancing sustainable practices against resource constraints and external shocks?

Policy Mechanisms and Partnerships

- What novel policy mechanisms, including public-private partnerships and adaptive governance models, can ensure long-term support, scalability, and innovation for environmentally sustainable micro-enterprises?

Empowering Entrepreneurs

- How can micro-entrepreneurs (especially from vulnerable populations) be empowered to set up realistic, stepwise, and resilient plans for green transitions?
- How can training programs, mentorship, and collaborative platforms help entrepreneurs balance immediate financial needs with long-term sustainability goals?

2.5 Theme 5: Inclusive and Sustainable Food Systems

This theme addresses the intersection of food systems, inequality, and sustainability, with a particular focus on affordability, gender+, and community-based action. It explores how participation in Bottom-Up Initiatives (BUIs) fosters behavioural and dietary changes, while also examining the structural barriers that limit access to healthy and sustainable food. The theme contributes to understanding how food policy and practice can support just transitions.

2.5.1 Relevant Findings

- Participation in Bottom-Up Initiatives (BUIs) is related to behavioural changes in food values and consumption. Specifically, participants took more into consideration health and environmental (animal) welfare when choosing their food and reported higher consumption of plant-based and locally produced food. BUIs are also important for fostering community engagement and solidarity, as they offer a platform for individuals to connect, share resources, and promote collective goals for sustainability. This engagement strengthens social networks and enhances feelings of empowerment and belonging within the community. Despite their potential, BUIs struggle to reach socially vulnerable groups effectively, as they predominantly attract middle and upper-middle-class participants. Resistance among marginalized groups often arises from structural inequalities, creating challenges for BUIs to reach all vulnerable populations effectively. For instance, historical distrust and socioeconomic vulnerabilities prevent equitable access to community initiatives.
- Affordability and accessibility are crucial challenges that hinder the ability of socially vulnerable groups to adopt more sustainable food practices. Financial constraints make it difficult for these groups to access healthier, locally produced, or plant-based foods, which are often perceived as more expensive compared to conventional options. Systemic inequalities, such as poor access to food distribution networks and limited economic resources, exacerbate these challenges. These systemic barriers often prevent marginalized populations from reaping the benefits of sustainability initiatives, as they may be excluded from the opportunities offered by BUIs due to factors like cost, time, and social capital.
- Motherhood emerges as a powerful motivator for sustainable food choices, as mothers often feel a strong sense of responsibility for their children's health and well-being. This concern for their children's future drives many mothers to make more environmentally conscious and health-oriented food decisions, even in the face of time constraints. Feminist ideologies also play a significant role in empowering women to take an active role in the ecological movement (Rocheleau, et al., 2013). Women involved in BUIs or community-driven sustainability projects often gain confidence and agency, which is enhanced by the solidarity they experience within their communities. This empowerment is crucial for fostering long-term behavioural changes that promote sustainability at both the individual and collective levels.
- Community networks and social capital play a central role in supporting the success of BUIs. As seen in the case studies, individuals who are part of

supportive social networks are more likely to engage in sustainable food behaviours and participate in BUIs.

- Community gardens (CGs) have emerged as vital community spaces that promote social cohesion, environmental sustainability, and food security, particularly for vulnerable groups. ACCTING's Pilot projects have demonstrated how digital platforms can enhance knowledge exchange, collaboration, and resource sharing among CG participants. CGs contribute to urban development by addressing intersectional inequalities and offering ecosystem services, such as urban cooling, biodiversity enhancement, and stormwater management. Yet, these benefits are often underacknowledged.

2.5.2 Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Role of Bottom-Up Initiatives in Sustainable Food Systems

While BUIs have shown promise in changing food behaviours, limited research exists on how these initiatives can be adapted and scaled to suit diverse socio-economic and geographical contexts. The current focus predominantly on urban and peri-urban areas leaves a gap in understanding how BUIs may be applied to rural food systems, where challenges may differ in terms of access, infrastructure, and resources.

- How do bottom-up initiatives (BUIs) facilitate transformative sustainable food behavioural changes among the most vulnerable communities, and how do these behaviours intersect with broader socio-economic and cultural contexts that condition these processes?
- What structural, institutional, and contextual factors enable or constrain the scalability and sustainability of BUIs across diverse rural and urban landscapes, and how do these dynamics vary across different socio-political environments?

Subtheme 2. Inclusivity in Sustainable Food Movements

Although BUIs have great potential, their accessibility to socially vulnerable groups remains limited. Further research is needed to explore how initiatives can better integrate vulnerable populations, particularly those who are most at risk of food insecurity and environmental degradation. This research should also focus on gender+ considerations, with the goal of fostering inclusivity and challenging existing power structures within the food system.

- What strategies can improve the inclusion of socially vulnerable groups in sustainable food movements?
- How can gender+ considerations be operationalized in food system initiatives to challenge entrenched power dynamics and promote transformative equity across all levels of the supply chain?
- What innovative communication models can leverage behavioural insights and cultural specificity to engage low-income and the most socially vulnerable populations in co-creating sustainable food systems?

Subtheme 3. Technological Interventions for Sustainable Food Systems

Digital tools and technologies offer a new avenue for empowering marginalized groups in food systems. However, limited exploration has been done on how these technologies can promote inclusivity and bridge the gap between food producers and consumers. There is also a need to assess whether low-tech solutions can provide viable alternatives that are more accessible and scalable in marginalized or resource-poor communities.

- How can emerging digital tools and platforms be strategically designed and implemented to foster equitable connections between food producers and vulnerable consumer groups, addressing issues of accessibility, affordability, and trust?
- What socio-technical, economic, and cultural factors influence the adoption and sustained use of digital agriculture technologies among the most vulnerable populations, and how can these be leveraged to create inclusive and resilient agricultural systems?
- How do low-tech solutions contribute to inclusivity and equal access to sustainable food systems? Could low-tech solutions offer scalable, cost-effective ways to support sustainability initiatives, especially in marginalized or resource-poor communities?

Subtheme 4. Rural Food Systems and Intersectional Vulnerabilities

Rural communities face unique challenges in adopting sustainable practices due to their geographical isolation, lack of infrastructure, and lower access to resources (Anastasiou et al., 2021). More research is needed to understand the intersectional vulnerabilities faced by rural populations and how tailored approaches can be developed to enhance their resilience and food security.

- How do rural-specific vulnerabilities impact the adoption of sustainable practices, and what tailored approaches can be developed to enhance resilience and food security in these communities?

Subtheme 5. Measuring Impact and Adaptability

Gender+ perspectives remain underrepresented in food system research and initiatives, and innovative methodologies are needed to assess the effectiveness of BUIs and other sustainability initiatives. Future research should focus on developing tools that can measure the long-term impact of these initiatives, particularly in terms of food equity and gender equality.

- What innovative methodologies can be developed to measure the impacts of BUIs on food equity?
- How can BUIs be made resilient to changing environmental, economic, and political conditions?

Subtheme 6. Political and Structural Barriers in Sustainable Food Systems

Political ideologies play a significant role in shaping sustainability efforts, often creating structural barriers that hinder or support environmentally sustainable practices. Political

choices can determine which policies are enacted and how sustainability initiatives are implemented, affecting their accessibility to vulnerable populations.

- Does political ideation create structural barriers related to environmental sustainability in modern societies? How do different political perspectives influence the accessibility and adoption of sustainable food practices in vulnerable communities?
- How can food waste practices in vulnerable communities contribute to accelerating environmental sustainability? Could food waste reduction be integrated into local food systems to create environmental, economic, and social benefits, especially for marginalized populations?

Subtheme 7. The Role of Fatherhood and Activism in Sustainable Food and Mobility Choices

The dynamics of family structures and caregiving roles, especially in relation to fatherhood and parenthood, are underexplored in terms of their influence on sustainable food practices. Fatherhood could play a significant role in motivating more sustainable food choices, particularly when it comes to concerns for children's health and the future. Additionally, activism in sustainable mobility has traditionally been associated with women, and more inclusive approaches are needed to engage men in sustainable transport initiatives.

- How can fatherhood (parenthood) be leveraged as a driver for behavioural change in adopting sustainable food practices? Could fathers' concerns for their children's health and the future play a role in shifting their food behaviours?
- Activism in sustainable mobility tends to be more associated with women than men. Could more inclusive activism approaches be developed that engage men in promoting sustainable transport practices, addressing gender disparities in eco-activism and mobility?

Subtheme 8. Indigenous Knowledge in Sustainable Food Systems

Indigenous knowledge plays a crucial role in fostering sustainable food systems. These communities have long practiced methods of environmental stewardship that align with the principles of sustainability, and these practices offer valuable insights into building more resilient food systems. The integration of indigenous knowledge can contribute to creating culturally sensitive and inclusive sustainability frameworks.

- How can indigenous knowledge be more fully integrated into sustainability research and practices, especially in relation to food systems, to promote a deeper understanding of environmental stewardship within marginalized communities?

2.6 Theme 6: Inclusive and Sustainable Mobility

Despite a substantial body of research illustrating how car dependency and transport policies disproportionately impact marginalized groups, the uptake of intersectional and gender-responsive approaches by policymakers remains limited. Many case studies detail successful inclusive and sustainable mobility initiatives, yet these examples are not consistently translated into policy. Key questions arise: What prevents policymakers and other privileged actors from integrating the knowledge and frameworks that already exist? How do political will, administrative structures, and broader socio-cultural norms influence whether and how equitable, sustainable measures are adopted?

Moreover, research on user behaviour often examines the experiences of marginalized communities, particularly in the context of transport poverty, exploring how they respond to or are affected by transport policies (e.g. Abelson et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021). While this type of research is crucial, future studies must also delve into policymaker behaviour and the structural or systemic barriers that inhibit equitable policy design, implementation, and enforcement. Understanding the motivations, resistances, and capacities of policymakers (and other influential stakeholders) will help bridge the gap between evidence-based recommendations and real-world policy outcomes.

2.6.1 Relevant Findings

1. Car Dependency and Resistance to Change

Car dependency results from the interdependent relationships of social, cultural, political, historical, geographical and technical systems (Urry, 2004). This includes both structural (such as urban planning and infrastructure that prioritize car use), social and cultural (that frame cars as symbols of freedom, masculinity, and a “good life,” often leading to resistance when restrictions on car use are proposed) and policy and political factors (that may fail to provide viable alternatives, limiting policymakers’ willingness or ability to impose restrictions on private car use).

Policies aimed at reducing car use can face public or political resistance if alternatives (e.g., accessible public transport) are insufficiently funded or poorly designed. The lack of affordable and convenient transportation alternatives discourages people from reducing car use. Moreover, transport choices are shaped not only by the availability of accessible options but also by constraints in transport infrastructure that support active mobility, such as walking and cycling, as well as socioeconomic limitations and living conditions. (Plyushteva and Schwanen, 2018).

2. Disproportionate Impact on Marginalised Groups

Marginalised populations, including low-income individuals, elderly people, and disabled persons, disproportionately bear the burden of car-free policies due to limited resources to adapt. For example, low-emission zones force economically disadvantaged groups to

upgrade their vehicles where few or no sustainable alternatives exist, a cost they cannot always afford (Kiss, 2022). However, policy-level failures, for instance, not incorporating equity-focused measures or ignoring intersectional vulnerabilities, can exacerbate negative impacts. Even when gender+ and intersectional research provides robust evidence, these insights do not always translate into inclusive policy design.

Public transport systems in many regions do not adequately address the mobility needs of disadvantaged populations. Women are more dependent on public transport and other non-car modes than men due to a number of factors, including unbalanced economic conditions (still more men than women own and have access to private cars), the strong connection between men, masculinity and cars, time-spatial organisation of work and everyday life. Men show stronger resistance to car-free policies because of cultural associations between cars and autonomy or status have tended to favour those transport patterns associated with men and masculinity and less so those associated with women's needs and their disproportionated care responsibilities.

3. Patterns of Public Response and Policy Design

Policies are often perceived as being implemented in a top-down manner, with limited community engagement or consultation. Disadvantaged groups feel, and often are, particularly excluded from decision-making processes, even when they are most affected by sustainable transport policies. In some cases, their marginal position also limits the extent to which they are affected by these policies (for example, if they do not own a car). Distrust is heightened by perceptions of hidden agendas, such as prioritizing revenue generation over public well-being. Privileged groups, on the other hand, can mount stronger resistance (e.g., lobbying against car-free zones) or simply circumvent restrictions (e.g., by purchasing electric vehicles). From a policy-learning perspective, the tension lies in developing strategies that encourage genuine engagement and address community-specific needs without simply yielding to the most vocal or financially influential groups.

Citizens' responses to car-free policies can vary widely, ranging from positive adaptation to active resistance. Disadvantaged groups may find it more difficult to take an active stance, for example due to resource constraints or the presence of other more pressing priorities, while groups that are relatively less exposed to social and economic hardship tend to be more vocal in their opposition, especially when policies restrict car use without providing viable alternatives for them. It is not uncommon for affluent people to escape car-free measures by adopting individual solutions (e.g. by buying electric cars that also allow access to low emission zones or paying for expensive parking or congestion charges). Although one goal of these measures is to reduce or replace petrol vehicles with cleaner alternatives, such actions limit the benefits aimed from these policies such as congestion or noise reduction. Gender also matters. For example, women are more likely than men to support car-free policies, be concerned about environmental issues, adopt or maintain sustainable mobility behaviour, and be open to sustainable mobility in general.

Policies with visible infrastructural benefits, such as improved public transport or the installation of bike lanes, gain better public reception than purely regulatory measures like low-emission zones, also because people perceive the latter as more reversible and easier to change than the former. Successful initiatives emphasize participatory processes

that address equity, accessibility, and community-specific needs while delivering immediate benefits like reduced congestion and better transport services. This fosters trust and long-term behavioural change.

4. Cycling as a Tool for Inclusive Mobility

Cycling initiatives are integral to achieving an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal by promoting access, competence, and embrace at personal, societal, and systemic levels (Gössling 2016; Lucas 2012). By promoting cycling and lowering barriers for cycling, cycling promotion initiatives contribute to reducing greenhouse gas emissions, noise, and congestion while fostering active lifestyles.

However, marginalised groups face barriers such as costs, inadequate infrastructure, and lack of cycling skills. Gender, socioeconomic status, disabilities and ethnicity intersect to exacerbate these challenges, with cultural norms and societal expectations creating additional hurdles, especially for women and young girls with migrant backgrounds. While all cyclists are vulnerable in cities primarily designed for cars, some cyclists experience greater challenges within car-dominated transport systems, namely those who are both vulnerable and reliant on additional support (i.e., children, seniors, and disabled people).

Despite the potential for community-building and independence, broader societal barriers like unsafe traffic conditions limit cycling's long-term adoption. Gender-sensitive and separatist approaches (e.g., women-only bike schools) effectively address specific cultural and gendered barriers.

5. Behavioural and Systemic Impacts of Mobility Policies

Participants in targeted mobility initiatives, such as bike schools, report increased confidence, competence, and independence. Social aspects, such as breaking social isolation and building community are other impacts of importance along with mobility skills taught, that lowered barriers for cycling.

Scaling these initiatives to meet European Green Deal goals remains challenging due to inconsistent regional support and infrastructure. Recommendations highlight the importance of participatory policy design, targeted investments, and addressing systemic barriers to ensure equity and sustainability. Understanding policymaker motivations, organizational structures, and potential barriers is key to embedding these initiatives within broader mobility strategies.

2.6.2 Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Sustainability and Behavioural Transformation

In the context of transport poverty, much of the existing studies often examines the experiences and behaviour of marginalized communities, while overlooking policy-level actors and their role in shaping sustainable transport measures. There is also an insufficient understanding of how and why policy changes occur in some contexts but not in others, despite extensive evidence on the importance of gender+ and intersectionality.

Research Questions:

1. Policymaker and Institutional Behaviour:

- What institutional, political, and cultural factors enable policymakers to propose, sustain, or scale up car-free and other sustainable transport policies in some contexts but not in others?
- What can be learned from successful policy change in terms of replicating or adapting effective interventions elsewhere?

2. Policy-Level Change for Collective Practices

- Which regulatory frameworks and policy tools can effectively encourage collective mobility practices while maintaining fairness, preventing unintended consequences, and ensuring that disadvantaged groups are not marginalized, thereby fostering inclusive benefits for all citizens?

3. Gendered Perceptions and Cultural Dynamics

- To what extent are gendered and cultural perceptions (e.g., cars as symbols of masculinity, trip-chaining requirements for women) shifting, and what targeted policy interventions can effectively address these shifting perceptions?
- What are the main sources of resistance (both within policymaking circles and among the public) to implementing policies that address gendered mobility needs, and how do these differ across cultural contexts?

4. Unintended and Indirect Effects

- What unintended consequences (both positive and negative) arise when implementing car-free or low-car policies (e.g., reinforcing inequalities, fostering new forms of civic engagement), and how can policymakers anticipate and mitigate them?
- How do policy approaches (including consultation processes, funding mechanisms, and partnerships with civil society) shape these outcomes?

Subtheme 2: Intersectionality in Mobility Transition

Although a wealth of research examines how overlapping vulnerabilities (e.g., socioeconomic, gender, ethnicity) shape mobility experiences, policymaking processes often do not systematically integrate intersectional findings into transport policies. Recent work (e.g., Bueno Patin & Stapper, 2025; EU Horizon Europe projects) shows that intersectionality is increasingly acknowledged in theory. However, questions remain about how to encourage more consistent application of these insights in practice. Identifying the institutional, cultural, and political factors that shape the uptake of intersectional approaches can inform strategies to close the gap between research and policy implementation.

Research Questions:

1. Institutional Factors and Knowledge Utilization

- What institutional, administrative, or cultural dynamics make it challenging for policymakers to consistently apply intersectional research when designing and implementing mobility policies?

- How can co-designed intervention studies—involving both researchers and policymakers—test and refine practical methods for translating intersectional insights into actionable policies?

2. Challenges in Implementation and Pathways to Change

- Which challenges (e.g., political priorities, resource limitations, stakeholder alignment) commonly arise when introducing intersectional mobility policies, and how can they be addressed or mitigated?
- To what extent can corporate and industry actors—through corporate social responsibility or public-private partnerships—support the development and uptake of equity-focused mobility solutions? (see, e.g., Boström, 2020; Koistinen et al., 2022)
- How can cooperative planning and participatory processes (with vulnerable groups, NGOs, local communities) strengthen policy relevance, ensuring that policies align more closely with on-the-ground realities?

3. Gender+ Inclusion

- Does increased gender+ diversity among policymakers (transport officials, urban planners, street-level bureaucrats) correlate with more inclusive policy measures and stronger utilization of intersectional frameworks?
- Which institutional mechanisms—such as diversity mandates, targeted hiring, or enhanced public consultation—have the greatest potential to foster inclusive policymaking processes?
- How can a more diverse policy environment facilitate better engagement with marginalized communities, supporting co-creation and more equitable outcomes?

4. Digital Access and the Adoption of Sustainable Mobility Solutions

- How do digital access and literacy (or lack thereof) affect the ability of marginalized groups to adopt app-based public transport systems, bike-sharing platforms, and other technology-driven mobility innovations?
- Which policy interventions or community-based programs most effectively bridge digital divides, ensuring that new mobility solutions are equitable and accessible to all?

Subtheme 3: Participatory Policy Design and Urban Planning

Although there is a good number of studies on co-design processes that involve both citizens and policymakers, much of the existing research relies on single-case or small-N comparative approaches. This creates a gap in understanding how co-design is planned, implemented, and evaluated across diverse political and cultural settings, and which factors promote or hinder larger-scale adoption of participatory policymaking. A systematic, large-N comparative perspective could yield valuable insights into how local authorities navigate resource constraints, political pressures, and cultural differences to adopt or avoid co-design approaches in urban transport planning.

Research Questions:

1. Large-N Comparative Studies and Cross-Cultural Variations

- How can larger-N or cross-national comparative analyses reveal patterns of success or failure in participatory approaches, especially in terms of equity and sustainability outcomes?
- In what ways do political structures (e.g., centralized vs. decentralized governance), cultural norms, and administrative capacities shape the effectiveness of co-design in different regional contexts?
- How might best practices be scaled up or adapted to ensure participatory policy design remains responsive to varied local realities?

2. Local Policy-Making Perspective: Enablers and Barriers

- What institutional, administrative, and political factors at the local level influence whether co-design processes are initiated or sustained in urban transport planning?
- How do local policymakers weigh potential benefits (e.g., broader support, improved legitimacy) against perceived risks (e.g., increased complexity, potential conflict) when deciding whether to adopt co-design methods?

3. Mitigating Environmental-Social Tensions and Protest Dynamics

- How can co-design processes help moderate tensions between social and environmental priorities, including resistance from groups that may be torn between different values (e.g., social justice vs. strict environmental measures)?
- Under what conditions do protest movements aligned with or against sustainable mobility measures gain or lose momentum, and how can participatory policy design address grievances (specific worries, fears, or disagreements people have about mobility policies) to foster more inclusive outcomes?

Subtheme 4: Environmental and Public Health Impacts

Extensive research demonstrates that reducing car dependency in urban environments can improve physical, mental, and social well-being (Saunders et al., 2013; Gössling & Choi, 2015). Walking and cycling, for instance, have been linked to lower rates of obesity, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes, as well as reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression. Beyond individual health, improved air quality and reduced noise pollution in areas with fewer cars contribute to better respiratory health, healthier sleep patterns, and greater social cohesion (Gehl, 2010; Nieuwenhuijsen, 2018).

Despite these well-documented benefits, not all population groups experience them equally. Low-income and marginalized communities often have limited access to safe, convenient active transport infrastructure, while women and older adults may face additional barriers related to safety, cultural norms, or mobility constraints (Braun et al., 2019). Consequently, the challenge is not just proving that reduced car use has positive health outcomes—this is widely acknowledged—but ensuring equitable access to those benefits across diverse demographics and different urban contexts. Questions remain about the most effective policy interventions, how these interventions vary by context, and how to equitably distribute the resulting health benefits.

Research Questions:

1. Comparative Effectiveness of Interventions

- Which policy measures (e.g., dedicated bike lanes, congestion charges, car-free zones) most effectively promote physical, mental, and social health, and how do these effects differ across contexts and population groups?

2. Equitable Distribution of Health Benefits

- How different types of transport interventions (e.g., congestion pricing, low-emission zones, improved cycling infrastructure) influence health outcomes for specific demographic groups?
- Which contextual factors (e.g. local governance structures, cultural norms, or existing inequalities) affect the success and replicability of these interventions?

2.7 Theme 7: Complexity of Intersectional Vulnerabilities

This transversal theme highlights how multiple dimensions of vulnerability—such as gender, race, disability, class, and migration status—intersect to shape exclusion from Green Deal policies and practices. It argues for a structural approach to intersectionality that moves beyond additive models and foregrounds systemic disadvantage. The aim is to support research and policy frameworks that are responsive to the lived realities of multiply marginalised individuals and communities

2.7.1 Relevant Findings

Intersectional vulnerabilities refer to the overlapping social, economic, and cultural disadvantages that individuals face due to multiple intersecting identities. These layers of marginalization compound one another, creating unique forms of exclusion or hardship that a single-axis approach (e.g., focusing on gender alone) often fails to capture.

In the context of sustainability transitions, this means that a low-income, immigrant woman entrepreneur, for example, may experience not just the constraints of insufficient financial resources but also language barriers, discrimination, and limited social networks, all of which undermine her ability to adopt or benefit from green solutions (Malisetti and Singh, 2024). These compounded vulnerabilities reduce access to credit, training, and policy support, making it harder to invest in sustainable technologies or practices. Moreover, many existing sustainability frameworks or policy instruments fail to account for the interplay of socio-cultural factors that shape people's willingness and capacity to engage.

As a result, minimal understanding exists of how these overlapping identities interact to produce challenges that are more than the sum of their parts. Empirical research rarely disaggregates data to recognize and address specific layers of marginalization. Consequently, well-intentioned initiatives risk reinforcing or exacerbating inequalities by overlooking the barriers that intersectionally vulnerable groups face. To build truly inclusive pathways toward environmental sustainability, future research and policy must better capture the lived realities of people experiencing multifaceted disadvantages, ensuring that strategies account for the full complexity of intersectional vulnerability.

2.7.2 Research Questions

1. Mapping Overlapping Vulnerabilities

- How do overlapping vulnerabilities (e.g., disability, migrant status, and gender) amplify barriers in transition to Green Deal?
- How can these complex challenges be systematically mapped and addressed?

2. Converging top-down and bottom-up

- What enabling conditions allow top-down policies and bottom-up resilience strategies to converge, ensuring that local participatory processes (enriched by gender-sensitive planning, private-sector CSR programs, and robust support for vulnerable groups) collectively advance broader “Green Deal” objectives for an inclusive green transition?

3. Discussion and Cross-Cutting Considerations

The findings of this second-cycle report underscore the interconnected nature of social, economic, and environmental challenges inherent in shaping an inclusive and sustainable transition under the European Green Deal framework. Throughout the research activities, Open Studios, and Pilot Actions, a recurring theme has been the extent to which contextual factors (ranging from local knowledge bases and cultural norms to institutional readiness and policy environments) mediate the success or failure of Green Deal related interventions. Below, we discuss the central points that emerged from these processes, highlighting theoretical implications, practical considerations, and areas requiring further investigation.

3.1 Interplay Between Local Knowledge and Institutional Frameworks

One of the most prominent issues emerging from the second cycle is the persistent gap between community-level insights and formal policy strategies. Although grassroots actors and local organizations often possess critical contextual knowledge (e.g., regarding resource constraints, social norms, and infrastructural limitations), institutional mechanisms for integrating such expertise remain insufficient or under-resourced. This dynamic highlights a tension between top-down policymaking — where guidelines and regulations are often standardized for broad applicability — and bottom-up, place-based solutions that are more responsive to local complexities. Balancing the two requires flexible policy instruments, capacity-building for local agencies, and iterative forms of collaboration that adapt as conditions evolve.

3.2 Intersectionality, Equity, and Social Inclusion

The second-cycle findings reinforce the importance of analysing climate-related strategies through an intersectional lens. Community members' socio-economic status, gender, race or ethnicity, and other axes of identity frequently converge to produce disproportionately high burdens of environmental and socio-economic risk. This recognition poses both methodological and policy-oriented challenges: first, ensuring that data collection is nuanced enough to capture overlapping vulnerabilities; second, guaranteeing that policies neither sideline these vulnerabilities nor exacerbate existing inequities. The Pilot Actions showcased examples of community-led initiatives that recognize these complexities, such as women-led groups organizing around disaster risk reduction or migrant communities shaping locally adapted sustainability practices, yet it remains clear that institutional uptake of intersectional insights is still far from universal.

Understanding how these inequalities manifest in practice requires attention not only to structural barriers but also to the behavioural mechanisms and conditions that shape everyday decision-making in sustainability transitions.

3.3 Behavioural Insights and Systemic Change

A significant body of evidence collected during this phase underscores that individual behavioural shifts, whether in energy consumption, mobility choices, or food practices, must be supported by broader institutional and infrastructural conditions. For instance, while public awareness campaigns can prompt a certain degree of pro-environmental sentiment, long-term adoption hinges on economic viability, access to resources, and compatible policy ecosystems. The Pilot Actions provided tangible instances of how context-specific incentives, peer-learning, and community-driven governance structures can collectively enhance the uptake of sustainable behaviours. However, the realities on the ground also suggest that systemic constraints, such as insufficient funding for low-income households or bureaucratic hurdles for nascent social enterprises, can suppress these behavioural gains before they reach fruition.

3.4 Micro-Entrepreneurship and Social Innovation

The second-cycle research further highlighted the potential of micro-enterprises as catalysts for social innovation. In many of the participating communities, small-scale entrepreneurs displayed creativity and adaptability in deploying low-cost, context-appropriate sustainability solutions. Nevertheless, these entrepreneurial endeavours are often hindered by structural barriers, including limited access to capital, policy inconsistencies, and the absence of robust support networks. As evidenced in the Pilot Actions, even modest interventions—such as specialized training programs, enhanced access to microcredit, or cooperative platforms—can significantly boost entrepreneurial resilience. This emphasis on systemic enablers aligns with previous arguments that localized, bottom-up innovation can only thrive within an environment attuned to social equity and institutional facilitation.

3.5 Cross-Sectoral Linkages and Multi-Level Governance

A key lesson from the second-cycle synthesis is the high degree of interdependency among sectors and governance levels. Initiatives aimed at improving disaster risk reduction can overlap significantly with those focusing on inclusive energy transitions, as robust social networks, adaptable organizational structures, and empowered local actors are vital in both scenarios. This realization stresses the importance of multi-level governance models, wherein local, regional, national, and supranational agencies coordinate activities and share resources. Interdisciplinary collaborations, including the involvement of practitioners from health, urban planning, social services, and environmental management, emerged as a best-practice strategy. However, while these collaborations proved beneficial, they also revealed the complexities of reconciling multiple agendas and funding streams, further underscoring the need for integrated policy frameworks that do not function in silos.

3.6 Synthesis and Way Forward

The cross-cutting insights generated in this second phase of ACCTING demonstrate a paradigm of inclusive, context-specific, and adaptive governance for addressing climate challenges. Many of the innovative approaches documented here rely on cooperative strategies that blend formal policy support with grassroots leadership, especially in communities with historically limited access to formal resources. Yet the scalability of these strategies depends on policy willingness to embrace risk, facilitate knowledge sharing across sectors, and channel resources where they can catalyse the most transformative change. In this regard, the updated research agendas outlined in this report offer a framework for guiding future investigation, experimentation, and policy engagement. They underscore the necessity of sustained dialogue between researchers, policy actors, and community stakeholders, a dialogue that can illuminate the complexities of equitable climate action and chart more integrated pathways forward.

Despite the rich dataset collected, certain limitations persist. First, the localized nature of many Pilot Actions means that findings, while indicative of broader patterns, may not be universally applicable without adaptation. Second, while intersectionality and systemic barriers were central themes, more work is needed to map out how specific demographic factors, such as migrant status or age, interact with local political economies in shaping outcomes. Additionally, the evolving nature of Green Deal policies means that the research context is not static; ongoing policy shifts may open up new opportunities (e.g., changes in funding mechanisms) but can also introduce fresh uncertainties. Future research should therefore continue to employ flexible, adaptive methodologies capable of capturing these dynamics in real time.

4. Conclusions

This report has presented an updated framework of research agendas, arising from the second cycle of research and Open Studios, as well as the Pilot Actions within the ACCTING project. These activities have highlighted not only the complex interplay between policy interventions and social inequalities but also the critical role of participatory, collaborative methods in revealing contextual nuances and fostering more inclusive climate strategies. By examining real-world practices, the project has explained how social, economic, and gendered vulnerabilities interact with Green Deal objectives, underscoring the need for intersectional perspectives across all research themes.

A key achievement has been the identification and refinement of knowledge gaps that persist in both policy and scholarly domains. Drawing on second-cycle findings as well as the lived experiences of stakeholders involved in the Pilot Actions, ACCTING has demonstrated specific areas where deeper research is essential to inform equitable policy design. These areas include the integration of local knowledge into formal disaster management systems, the institutional barriers that hinder inclusive energy transitions, the intersectional dimensions of micro-entrepreneurship, and the need for sustainable food

and mobility models that genuinely benefit marginalized communities. The emergent seven research themes illustrate the diversity and complexity of the topics at hand, from participatory policy design and behavioural change to the structural drivers of inequalities and resilience.

The refined set of future research agendas provides a pathway for continued examination and experimentation, ensuring that the inquiry remains closely aligned with both grassroots realities and overarching policy frameworks. By reinforcing the links between theoretical insights and practical interventions, these agendas are designed to inform, inspire, and support future collaborative efforts to realise a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable European Green Deal.

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